

Effect of Land Use on Soil Fertility in Galicia Based on LUCAS Data

The impact of land use on soil can be determined through the land-use information provided by the LUCAS database, which makes it possible to understand the processes resulting from the establishment of broadleaves, conifers, permanent grasslands, and shrublands. Using this database shows that, in the case of Galicia, there is a negative relationship between organic matter content and pH—something expected for the Galician region. Galicia is the area with the highest forest growth potential in Europe, which ensures the incorporation of organic matter into the soil. However, the rate of mineralization of that organic matter, and therefore its ability to be mineralized or remain stored in the soil, depends on pH. Under very acidic conditions, organic matter—and therefore organic carbon—tends to accumulate in the soil because microbial processes slow down. Nevertheless, as this pH increases, organic matter content decreases due to the activation of mineralization rates. Land use affects the main chemical components of soil health. Organic matter and nitrogen, which vary in parallel in multivariate analysis, show lower levels in permanent grasslands compared with shrublands (Figure 2). Conversely, P levels and pH in water are higher in shrublands compared with permanent grasslands. This can be explained by management practices, since permanent grasslands are typically fertilized with phosphorus and limed, unlike more forest related land uses. As mentioned earlier, liming reduces organic matter and therefore nitrogen related land uses. As mentioned

earlier, liming reduces organic matter and therefore nitrogen. The LUCAS database makes it possible to evaluate the long-term impact of land use on soil chemical variables. In the case of Galicia, the improvement of soil fertility as a source of nutrients and amendments leads to a decrease in organic matter—and consequently nitrogen—due to the increase in soil pH compared with forested areas term impact of land use on soil chemical variables. In the case of Galicia, the improvement of soil fertility as a source of nutrients and amendments leads to a decrease in organic matter—and consequently nitrogen—due to the increase in soil pH compared with forested areas.

Figure 1. Levels of nitrogen, phosphorus, pH in water, and organic carbon in different land uses based on LUCAS data in Galicia.

AUTHORSHIP

Mosquera-Losada, M.R.^a; Rodríguez-Rigueiro, F.J.^a; González-Hernández, M.P.^a; Romero-Franco R.^a; Fernández-Lorenzo, J.L.^a; Taboada-Iglesias, M.J.^b; Aldrey-Vázquez, J.A.^c; Alvarez-Rodríguez, E.^d; Ferreiro-Domínguez, N.^a

a) Department of Plant Production and Engineering Projects, Higher Polytechnic School of Lugo, University of Santiago de Compostela, 27002 Lugo, Spain; **b)** Department of Electronics and Computing, Higher Technical School of Engineering, University of Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain; **c)** Department of Geography, Faculty of Geography and History, University of Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain; **d)** Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, Higher Polytechnic School of Lugo, University of Santiago de Compostela, 27002 Lugo, Spain.